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Windsor and Obergefell as a Benchmark for Marriage Equality in Poland²

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Abstract:

Two landmark rulings of the Supreme Court of the United States in *Windsor v. United States* and *Obergefell v. Hodges* led to the full institutionalization of same-sex marriage in that country. The article contains a historical as well as a legal analysis of both those decisions. Furthermore, it reconstructs the arguments raised by the U.S. Supreme Court on the basis of Polish and international law to answer whether Polish courts could issue similar rulings.

Keywords: marriage equality, same-sex marriage, civil unions, constitutional law, international law, human rights, U.S. Supreme Court

Orzeczenia w sprawach *Windsor* i *Obergefell* jako punkt odniesienia dla równości małżeńskiej w Polsce

Dwa przełomowe orzeczenia Sądu Najwyższego Stanów Zjednoczonych w sprawach *Windsor v. United States* i *Obergefell v. Hodges* doprowadziły do pełnej instytucjonalizacji małżeństw jednopłciowych w tymże kraju. W artykule dokonano analizy historycznej oraz prawnej obu tych wyroków. Ponadto zrekonstruowano argumenty sformułowane przez amerykański Sąd Najwyższy na kanwie prawa polskiego oraz międzynarodowego, w celu odpowiedzi na pytanie, czy polskie sądy mogłyby orzec w podobny sposób.

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² Tekst nagrodzony w konkursie rekrutacyjnym do Szkoły Prawa Amerykańskiego UJ: „Słynne orzeczenia amerykańskie jako inspiracja dla prawa polskiego”, organizowanym przez KN Prawa Amerykańskiego TBSP UJ.

Słowa kluczowe: równość małżeńska, małżeństwa jedнопłciowe, związki partnerskie, prawo konstytucyjne, prawo międzynarodowe, prawa człowieka, Sąd Najwyższy USA

1. Introduction

Marriage equality, or legality of same-sex marriage, is a legal concept that has – in the recent years – become one of the largest points of dispute between liberal and conservative jurists. While some consider the ability to marry regardless of the partner’s gender a fundamental human right, others consider same-sex unions to be immoral and unnatural. In 2021, The Polish National Public Prosecutor’s Office (NPPO) went as far, as to call the potential legalization of same sex-marriage “a danger to the legal system and social order in Poland which would open a way for a future undermining of constitutional rules”³. The quote comes from a filing in a case, in which several gay rights activists called for the repeal of Article 1 §⁴ 1 of The Family and Guardianship Code – a provision which constrains the act of marriage to persons of opposite sex⁵. The NPPO joined the proceedings seeking an explicit ruling that the Polish Constitution precludes same-sex marriage. The Constitutional Tribunal⁶, however, ruled against the wishes of both parties and quietly dismissed the complaint on procedural grounds, as it has similarly done to but one case regarding marriage equality⁷. One of the Tribunal’s

³ K. Sobczak, *Prokuratura oczekuje wyroku sądu TK w sprawie związków jedнопłciowych*, para. 1, <<https://www.prawo.pl/prawo/zwiazki-jedнопłciowe-prokuratura-oczekuje-wyroku-sadu-tk,508849.html>>, [accessed: 20.3.2023].

⁴ The basic editorial unit of a Polish legal act, which expresses an independent thought, is an article (pol. “artykuł”, abbr. “art.”). If one independent thought is expressed by a set of different sentences, an article can be divided into further units. Such units found in ordinary legal acts are named “ustępy” (abbr. “ust.”) while in acts designated as Codes (pol. “Kodeksy”) they are named “paragrafy” (abbr. “§”). See Regulation of the Prime Minister of 20.6.2002 on the “Rules of Legislative Technique” (Journal of Laws of 2016, item 283, as amended). An issue arises when attempting to translate those inherently Polish subdivisions, as most English-speaking legal systems do not differentiate between same-level editorial units. Likewise, for the purposes of this paper I found no need to make a distinction between “ustępy” and “paragrafy.” Accordingly, both editorial units have been translated as “sections” (abbr. “§”).

⁵ Act of 25.2.1964 – The Family and Guardianship Code (consol. Journal of Laws of 2020, item 135, as amended), Article 1 § 1.

⁶ Since 2015 the composition of the Polish Constitutional Tribunal has been heavily contested due to irregularities in the appointment of three so-called “duplicate judges”. See Judgements of the ECtHR of 7.5.2021, Xero Flor w Polsce sp. z o.o. v. Poland, application no. 4907/18; of 23.11.2023, Wałęsa v. Poland, application no. 50849/21; and of 14.12.2023, M.L. v. Poland, application no. 40119/21. For the purposes of this paper, I avoid the use of negative terms relating to the Tribunal, such as “the neo-Tribunal” or “the Constitutional «Tribunal»”, as the composition of Poland’s constitutional court lies outside the scope of this work.

⁷ Orders of the Constitutional Tribunal (CT) of 1.7.2021, refs. SK 15/17 and SK 4/19; Orders of the CT of 15.12.2021, refs. SK 13/17, SK 14/17 and SK 9/19. See also: *Opinion of Ordo Iuris Institute for Legal Culture on case pending before the Constitutional Tribunal ref. SK 12/17*, Ordo Iuris Institute for Legal Culture 2022, <https://ipo.trybunal.gov.pl/ipo/dok?dok=bddf91f3-e15e-4ee9-b4bc-68048b10b515%2FSK_12_17_OI_2023_02_24_amcu_ADO.pdf>, [accessed: 30.1.2024].

Judges and its then-vice-president, Prof. Muszyński, has criticized those decisions, calling them “an opening of the Polish constitutional system to marriage of persons of the same sex”⁸. And yet, most countries (including Poland) still don’t offer any legal protections to same-sex couples. As of January 2024, the right of people to marry regardless of the partner’s gender is considered good law in nearly 40 countries, including (but not limited to) France, the United Kingdom, and the United States⁹. Whether Poland joins that list in the future remains to be seen. Even though the government has announced its intention to introduce an act legalizing the so-called “civil partnerships”, many remain skeptical. Among the unconvinced is the incumbent President, who – in the absence of a parliamentary supermajority – would ultimately have to give his assent for such an act to become law¹⁰. And while a legislative intervention appears unlikely, Polish gays and lesbians – inspired by similar measures in the United States – turn with hope to the judiciary. The point of this paper is to analyze the landmark decisions of the American Supreme Court in *United States v. Windsor* and *Obergefell v. Hodges* – which implemented marriage equality against explicit wishes of the lawmakers – and to reconstruct the arguments contained therein on the grounds of the Polish legal system. Furthermore, the paper aims to analyze whether it would be permissible for Polish courts to use such arguments in their own rulings.

2. A brief historical look at same-sex marriage in the U.S.

The United States’ path to marriage equality began on December 17, 1990, when three same-sex couples submitted applications for marriage licenses at the Hawaii Department of Public Health in Honolulu, which were – on the advice of the state’s Attorney General – turned down¹¹. At the time, homosexual marriage wasn’t a major political issue in the U.S. or anywhere in the world for the matter. Despite that fact, the couples filed a lawsuit (which bore the name *Baehr v. Lewin*) in the state’s First Circuit Court on May 1, 1991¹². The complaint was carefully crafted to avoid issues of federal law as the U.S. Supreme Court had upheld discriminatory sodomy laws in *Bowers v. Hardwick* just 5 years prior¹³. After a rather expeditious dismissal by the trial court, the couples appealed to the Supreme Court of Hawaii which, to the surprise of all,

⁸ *Ordo Iuris chce wyroku Trybunału Konstytucyjnego ws. par jednopłciowych*, para. 3, <<https://www.rp.pl/prawo-rodzinne/art38044901-or-do-iuris-chce-wyroku-trybunalu-konstytucyjnego-ws-par-jednopłciowych>>, [accessed: 20.3.2023].

⁹ *Marriage Equality Around the World*, Human Rights Campaign 2024, <<https://www.hrc.org/resources/marriage-equality-around-the-world>>, [accessed: 10.3.2024].

¹⁰ N. Senkowska, *Ustawa o związkach partnerskich coraz bliżej. Czy prezydent ją podpisze?*, para. 1, <<https://www.rp.pl/w-sadzie-i-w-urzedzie/art39707531-ustawa-o-zwiazkach-partnerskich-coraz-blizej-czy-prezydent-ja-podpisze>>, [accessed: 30.1.2024].

¹¹ S. Issenberg, *The Engagement: America’s Quarter-Century Struggle Over Same-Sex Marriage*, New York 2021, p. 28–31, 60, 65.

¹² S. Issenberg, *The Engagement...*, p. 69.

¹³ S. Issenberg, *The Engagement...*, p. 66–67. See also: Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 30.6.1986, *Bowers v. Hardwick*, 478 U.S. 186 (1986).

issued a ruling in their favor on May 5, 1993¹⁴. In a plurality opinion the court held that “[Hawaii Revised Statutes – M.C.] § 572–1, on its face, discriminates based on sex against the applicant couples in the exercise of the civil right of marriage, thereby implicating the equal protection clause of article I, section 5 of the Hawaii Constitution”¹⁵. The case was then remanded for further proceedings to determine whether such discrimination was permitted under the state’s strict scrutiny standard.

This decision by the Aloha State’s highest court amounted to a political earthquake the effects of which were felt all over the country. In 1996, in direct response to the *Baehr* ruling Congress passed the Defense of Marriage Act, which President Clinton subsequently signed into law¹⁶. The act consisted of three short sections, the first of which customarily contained its short name. The second provision was much more controversial, as it allowed the states not to recognize same sex marriages performed in other parts of the country. Finally, the last section of DOMA defined “marriage” as “a legal union between one man and one woman as husband and wife” for the purpose of all federal government regulations¹⁷. Just two years later, emboldened by Congress’ action, Hawaiian politicians decided to take a similar step. Following a referendum, the state constitution was amended, and the legislature was given “the power to reserve marriage to opposite sex couples”¹⁸. It exercised that power shortly after, thus making the *Baehr* case moot. Due to those events – the passage of DOMA and the ballot measure in Hawaii – as well as to the federal courts’ consistent refusal to recognize any legal form of same-sex unions¹⁹, the issue seemed to die down. And while in May 2004 the Commonwealth of Massachusetts became the first state to implement marriage equality, the opponents of same-sex marriage were much stronger in numbers²⁰. By 2011, people of same sex could marry in just six U.S. states while they were explicitly banned from doing so in more than half of them²¹.

However, DOMA would soon face its first serious court challenge, in the case of a woman named Edith Windsor. She and her spouse, Thea Spyer, were legally married in Canada, and the State of New York, where the two women resided, recognized that marriage as valid. Tragically, Spyer died in February 2009, making her wife the executor of her estate. However, due to § 3 of DOMA, Windsor did not qualify for a spousal tax exemption and was forced to pay over \$300.000 in federal estate tax.

¹⁴ S. Issenberg, *The Engagement...*, p. 74, 88–93.

¹⁵ Decision of the Supreme Court of Hawaii of 5.5.1993, *Baehr v. Lewin*, 74 Haw. 530 (Haw. 1993).

¹⁶ R. Socarides, *Why President Clinton Signed the Defense of Marriage Act*, para. 1, <<https://www.newyorker.com/news/news-desk/why-bill-clinton-signed-the-defense-of-marriage-act>>, [accessed: 21.3.2023].

¹⁷ Defense of Marriage Act, Pub. L. 104–119.

¹⁸ The Constitution of The State of Hawaii of 7.11.1950, art. I § 23.

¹⁹ See, e.g., Decision of the D.C. Circuit Court of Appeals of 19.1.1995, *Dean v. District of Columbia*, 653 A.2d 307 (1995).

²⁰ P. Belluck, *Massachusetts Arrives at Moment for Same-Sex Marriage*, <<https://www.nytimes.com/2004/05/17/us/massachusetts-arrives-at-moment-for-same-sex-marriage.html>>, [accessed: 22.3.2023].

²¹ N. Confessore, M. Barbaro, *New York Allows Same-Sex Marriage, Becoming Largest State to Pass Law*, <<https://www.nytimes.com/2011/06/25/nyregion/gay-marriage-approved-by-new-york-senate.html>>, [accessed: 23.3.2023].

Windsor sued, challenging the controversial provision as a violation of her Constitutional rights. The District Court, the 2nd Circuit Court of Appeals and ultimately the Supreme Court all agreed with her reasoning and DOMA § 3 was struck down²². Those decisions, however, did not resolve the issue. That's because even though the federal government could no longer discriminate based on sexual orientation; similar restrictions on the state level were left in place. That situation would change just two years after the highest court's decision in *Windsor*. In a landmark case brought by fourteen same-sex couples against the states of Michigan, Kentucky, Ohio, and Tennessee – which bore the name *Obergefell v. Hodges* – the Supreme Court in a 5–4 decision struck down the remaining provisions of DOMA and ordered all states to certify marriages between persons of the same sex²³.

The historical analysis shows us that marriage equality in the U.S. was not implemented on a top–down basis. The initiative originated at the state level, and gradually made its way to federal courts. Only in December 2022 – nearly thirty years after the first ruling in *Baehr* – did Congress decide to enshrine marriage equality into U.S. Code and ultimately repeal DOMA²⁴. Furthermore, at the time of the District Court's ruling in *Windsor* there was no national consensus in support of gay rights. A survey conducted by Pew Research Center shows that, at the time, the American society was heavily polarized on the issue, with 45% of Americans supporting marriage equality and 46% opposing it²⁵. However, a more recent (2023) Gallup poll shows that the support has risen by 26 pp in just over a decade²⁶. The courts' decisions, which were originally considered controversial, formed a new national consensus that stands strong to this day. In contrast, an Ipsos survey shows that the support for gay rights in Poland is already much higher than it was the U.S. a decade ago. According to the 2023 poll, 32% of Poles believe that same-sex couples should be allowed to marry legally, while 35% believe they should be allowed to obtain some other form of legal recognition (67% in support in total). Only 22% of Poles believe that same-sex couples deserve no legal recognition. Two groups particularly sympathetic to LGBT people are the youngest respondents (<35 years old) and women²⁷. The poll notes that the support for same-sex unions in Poland is gradually increasing, having risen by 11 pp since 2013.

²² Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2013, *United States v. Windsor*, 570 U.S. 744 (2013).

²³ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2015, *Obergefell v. Hodges*, 576 U.S. 644 (2015).

²⁴ Respect For Marriage Act, Pub. L. 117–228.

²⁵ *Growing Public Support for Same Sex Marriage*, Pew Research Center 2012, <<https://www.pewresearch.org/politics/2012/02/07/growing-public-support-for-same-sex-marriage>>, [accessed: 23.3.2023].

²⁶ J. McCarthy, *Same-Sex Marriage Support Holds at 71% High*, <<https://news.gallup.com/poll/393197/same-sex-marriage-support-inches-new-high.aspx>>, [accessed: 30.1.2024].

²⁷ *Większość Polaków chce legalizacji związków osób tej samej płci*, Ipsos 2023, <<https://www.ipsos.com/pl-pl/wiekszosc-polakow-chce-legalizacji-zwiazkow-osob-tej-samej-plci>>, [accessed: 28.1.2024].

3. Could the U.S. Supreme Court's gay-rights decisions really become a benchmark for marriage equality in Poland?

Having considered the historical and social background of same-sex marriage in the United States, we now turn to legal analysis. At the very start, it should be emphasized that the U.S. and Poland are countries with legal systems and cultures that differ profoundly from one another. Due to historical reasons, Americans find individual freedoms – such as the freedom of speech or the right to privacy – to be much of much greater importance than in most European countries. One must also consider the drastic difference in discretionary power vested upon Polish and American courts. Finally, it should be noted that the Polish Constitution – unlike its U.S. counterpart – contains an explicit definition of marriage. Therefore, an obvious question arises – can Polish judges actually use the same reasoning as the American Supreme Court in *Windsor* and *Obergefell*? Or is such argumentation doomed to fail? In an attempt to find an answer, we ought to look into the majority opinions in both *Windsor* and *Obergefell* and attempt to reconstruct some of the Justices' arguments on the grounds of Polish law.

The Supreme Court's 26-page decision in *United States v. Windsor* was authored by Justice Anthony Kennedy, who notes that "The Constitution's guarantee of equality 'must at the very least mean that a bare congressional desire to harm a politically unpopular group cannot' justify disparate treatment of that group"²⁸. This guarantee comes from the Due Process Clause of the 5th Amendment, which states that "no person shall (...) be deprived of life, liberty, or property, without due process of law"²⁹. The now-retired Justice's decision points out that "DOMA's principal effect is to identify a subset of state sanctioned marriages and make them unequal. The principal purpose is inequality, not for other reasons like governmental efficiency"³⁰. Kennedy further writes that "by its great reach, DOMA" among others "prevents same-sex married couples from obtaining government healthcare benefits (...) deprives them of the Bankruptcy Code's special protections (...) forces them to follow a complicated procedure to file their state and federal taxes jointly (...) and it denies or reduces benefits allowed to the families upon the loss of a spouse and parent"³¹. The majority finally concludes that "by seeking to displace this protection and treating those persons as living in marriages less respected than others, the federal statute is in violation of the Fifth Amendment"³², the keyword being "federal" as the *Windsor* ruling didn't bind state governments. The second decision – in *Obergefell v. Hodges* – was once again authored by Justice Kennedy³³. This time, however, the opinion wasn't based on the 5th Amendment, but rather on the Due

²⁸ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2013, *United States v. Windsor*, 570 U.S. 744 (2013), p. 20.

²⁹ Constitution of the United States of America of 17.9.1787, amend. V

³⁰ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2013, *United States v. Windsor*, 570 U.S. 744 (2013), p. 22–23.

³¹ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2013, *United States v. Windsor*, 570 U.S. 744 (2013), p. 23–24.

³² Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2013, *United States v. Windsor*, 570 U.S. 744 (2013), p. 26.

³³ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2015, *Obergefell v. Hodges*, 576 U.S. 644 (2015).

Process and Equal Protection Clauses of the 14th Amendment. The former of those provisions reads “nor shall any State deprive any person of life, liberty or property without due process of law”³⁴. Its text may appear practically indistinguishable from the analogous provision of the 5th Amendment, on which the decision in *Windsor* was based. However, the inclusion of the word “State” in the clause has been interpreted as an extension of the scope of due process. That’s because while the 5th Amendment has been understood to only apply to the federal government, the 14th Amendment incorporated its protections against the individual states. Meanwhile, the Equal Protection Clause reads “nor shall any State (...) deny to any person within its jurisdiction the equal protection of the laws” once again binding the state governments³⁵. As Justice Kennedy notes in *Obergefell* “The Due Process Clause and the Equal Protection Clause are connected in a profound way (...) In any particular case (...) the two Clauses may converge in the identification and definition of the right”³⁶. Kennedy then once again concludes that “the challenged laws burden the liberty of same-sex couples, and (...) abridge central precepts of equality. (...) And the Equal Protection Clause, like the Due Process Clause, prohibits this unjustified infringement of the fundamental right to marry”³⁷.

The protections which were the basis for both *Windsor* and *Obergefell* are not unknown to the Polish legal system. Chapter II of the Constitution of Poland enumerates the freedoms and rights of persons and citizens. Articles 38 and 46 guarantee the legal protection of life and property, respectively³⁸. Those same protections can be found in the Due Process Clause; they are however non-essential in the case of gay marriage. The more significant guarantee – that is the guarantee of personal liberty, is contained within Article 31 § 1. The provision states that the “freedom of the person shall receive legal protection”³⁹. This guarantee, however, is considered subsidiary to other constitutional rights as “it can only be an isolated and exclusive basis for determining a person’s constitutional position, when no other constitutional freedom or right can be referred to”⁴⁰. Such a right, to which we can appropriately refer, can be found in Article 32. The first section of this provision states that “All persons shall be equal before the law” and “All persons shall have the right to equal treatment by public authorities”⁴¹. Polish constitutionalists are consistent in interpreting this right not as “an obligation to create identical norms for all people and to enforce them identically in particular cases” but rather to “based on certain traits (...) determine which persons are situated

³⁴ Constitution of the United States of America of 17.9.1787, amend. XIV, § 1.

³⁵ Constitution of the United States of America of 17.9.1787, amend. XIV, § 1.

³⁶ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2015, *Obergefell v. Hodges*, 576 U.S. 644 (2015), p. 19.

³⁷ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2015, *Obergefell v. Hodges*, 576 U.S. 644 (2015), p. 22.

³⁸ The Constitution of The Republic of Poland of 2.4.1997 (Journal of Laws No. 78, item 483, as amended), Articles 38 and 46.

³⁹ The Constitution of The Republic of Poland of 2.4.1997 (Journal of Laws No. 78, item 483, as amended), Article 31 § 1.

⁴⁰ P. Tuleja [in:] *Konstytucja Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej. Komentarz*, ed. P. Tuleja, Warszawa 2023, commentary on Article 31.

⁴¹ The Constitution of The Republic of Poland of 2.4.1997 (Journal of Laws No. 78, item 483, as amended), Article 32 § 1.

similarly and should be treated equally by the law⁴². This “guarantee of equality under the law refers to the process of establishing legal norms and imposes on the legislator an obligation to implement such law, that satisfies the duty to treat similar subjects (situations) equally⁴³. This provision, even though it expresses the right idea, is still not what we’re looking for. That’s because it only “expresses a general rule and should always be referring to particular provisions of the Constitution” and as such “cannot be protected by a constitutional complaint⁴⁴. However, Article 32 contains a second section, which states that “no one shall be discriminated against in political, social or economic life for any reason whatsoever⁴⁵, where discrimination is defined as an “unfounded differentiation of persons based on their objective traits (...) such as gender, age, social background or **sexual preferences** [emphasis – M.C.]⁴⁶. The Polish Constitution is particularly broad, as it doesn’t enumerate such objective traits, but rather outright forbids discrimination “for any reason”. The provision of Article 32 § 2, which precludes the government from treating people unequally, is precisely the norm we’re looking for, as it entails the same idea as the opinions in *Windsor* and *Obergefell*. After all, the first of those decisions struck down a federal law for “writing inequality into the entire United States Code⁴⁷ while the second one voided four state statutes which “demean[ed] gays and lesbians⁴⁸. It is undeniable, that if the government confers some privileges on opposite-sex couples – such as tax benefits, marital property systems or the right to a burial – while refusing to accommodate same-sex couples, the treatment can be considered inherently unequal or even demeaning. And while some people may belittle the value of such governmental aid, the case of Edith Windsor shows us that the losses same-sex couples suffer can reach hundreds of thousands of dollars if not more.

However, one ought to consider whether applicability of Article 32 § 2 in cases of same-sex marriage is precluded by Article 18 of the Constitution. The provision states that “marriage, being a union of man and a woman (...) shall be placed under the protection and care of the Republic”. In the doctrine of constitutional law one can find three competing concepts concerning the interpretation of this provision⁴⁹. The first approach – expressed, among others, in the comment edited by Prof. Safjan and Prof. Bosek – is that “the substance of Article 18 [...] is the establishment of a ban addressed to the legislature which forbids the registration of de facto unions between two individuals (regardless of the sex of the persons in them) other than in the character

⁴² P. Tuleja [in:] *Konstytucja...*, commentary on Article 32.

⁴³ L. Garlicki, M. Zubik [in:] *Konstytucja Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej. Komentarz*, vol. II, ed. L. Garlicki, M. Zubik, Warszawa 2016, commentary on Article 32.

⁴⁴ Order of the CT of 24.10.2001, ref. SK 10/01.

⁴⁵ The Constitution of The Republic of Poland of 2.4.1997 (Journal of Laws No. 78, item 483, as amended), Article 32 § 2.

⁴⁶ Order of the CT of 24.10.2001, ref. SK 10/01.

⁴⁷ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2013, *United States v. Windsor*, 570 U.S. 744 (2013), p. 22.

⁴⁸ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2015, *Obergefell v. Hodges*, 576 U.S. 644 (2015), p. 17.

⁴⁹ P. Tuleja [in:] *Konstytucja...*, commentary on Article 18.

of marriage. These, in turn, have been restricted only to unions between men and women⁵⁰. This belief was once dominant among scholars. Meanwhile, Prof. Garlicki – a representative of the so-called relativized approach – believes that “the preclusion/acceptance of the legalization of civil unions depends on their proximity to the institution of heterosexual marriage (...) Article 18 sets, as it were, a ceiling of similarities which the ordinary legislator cannot exceed”⁵¹. This approach appears to be the most common among Polish constitutionalists nowadays, according to Prof. Tuleja⁵². It must be noted that both interpretations make it impossible to implement true marriage equality. This conclusion stems from the argument that Article 18 infers upon the legislator a duty to issue special guarantees and protections to heterosexual marriages. On this assumption, same-sex unions – should the legislature decide to implement them – would always be at a disadvantaged position. Finally, there is a third approach, although is the least prevalent of them all. It stems from particular rulings of Polish courts, such as a 2019 decision of the Regional Administrative Court in Warsaw, which has since been affirmed by the Supreme Administrative Court (SAC)⁵³, noting that “Art. 18 of the Constitution could not by itself constitute an obstacle, which would prevent the transcription of a foreign marriage certificate, should the national legal system provide for an institution of [same-sex marriage]. Furthermore, the aforementioned provision doesn’t forbid the legislature, from institutionalizing civil unions of people of same or different sex by statute (...)”⁵⁴.

To sum up, the dispute regarding Article 18 is still unresolved. Polish constitutionalists remain heavily split on the issue and an acceptable consensus is nowhere to be reached⁵⁵. Nevertheless, even Prof. Łętowska and Prof. Woleński – some of the staunchest supporters of same-sex unions among Polish jurists – argued for a statutory implementation of such unions, and not a judicial one⁵⁶. Similar notion can be found in the aforementioned decision of the Administrative Court in Warsaw, which noted that “the will of the legislature is decisive in this matter”⁵⁷. Such a view is also consistent with past

⁵⁰ W. Borysiak [in:] *Konstytucja RP. Tom I. Komentarz do art. 1–86*, ed. M. Safjan, L. Bosek, Warszawa 2016, commentary on Article 18, paras. 122–126.

⁵¹ L. Garlicki [in:] *Konstytucja Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej. Komentarz*, vol. I, ed. L. Garlicki, M. Zubik, Warszawa 2016, commentary on Article 18.

⁵² P. Tuleja [in:] *Konstytucja...*, commentary on Article 18, sec. 8, para. 4.

⁵³ Judgment of the Supreme Administrative Court (SAC) of 6.7.2022, ref. II OSK 2376/19.

⁵⁴ Judgment of the Regional Administrative Court in Warsaw of 8.1.2019, ref. IV SA/Wa 2618/18.

⁵⁵ See: E. Łętowska, J. Woleński, *Instytucjonalizacja związków partnerskich a Konstytucja RP z 1997 r.*, „Państwo i Prawo” 2013, no. 6, p. 15–40 arguing for the statutory institutionalization of same-sex partnerships. See also: M. Wyrzykowski, *Publiczne a prywatne w wykładni konstytucyjnej na przykładzie art. 18 Konstytucji* [in:] *Interes publiczny a interes prywatny w prawie*, ed. T. Giaro, Warszawa 2012, p. 215–233. To the contrary see e.g.: B. Banaszekiewicz, *Problem konstytucyjnej oceny instytucjonalizacji związków homoseksualnych*, „Kwartalnik Prawa Prywatnego” 2004, no. 2, p. 359–386; A. Mączyński, *Konstytucyjne i międzynarodowe uwarunkowania instytucjonalizacji związków homoseksualnych* [in:] *Związki partnerskie – debata na temat projektowych zmian prawnych*, ed. M. Andrzejewski, Toruń 2012.

⁵⁶ E. Łętowska, J. Woleński, *Instytucjonalizacja...*, p. 16.

⁵⁷ Judgment of the Regional Administrative Court in Warsaw of 8.1.2019, ref. IV SA/Wa 2618/18.

rulings of the Constitutional Tribunal, which conclude that when “the legislature knowingly leaves a certain matter fully outside the scope of legal regulations”, such legislative neglect does not lie in the Tribunal’s jurisdiction⁵⁸. The fact that same-sex unions are not institutionalized in Polish law is thus nonjusticiable⁵⁹.

The idea that the courts ought to wait for a legislative intervention was, however, heavily criticised by the majority in *Obergefell*. As Justice Kennedy wrote:

There may be an initial inclination in these cases to proceed with caution—to await further legislation, litigation, and debate. The respondents warn there has been insufficient democratic discourse before deciding an issue so basic as the definition of marriage. (...) Yet there has been far more deliberation than this argument acknowledges. There have been referenda, legislative debates, and grassroots campaigns, as well as countless studies, papers, books, and other popular and scholarly writings. There has been extensive litigation in state and federal courts. ... Judicial opinions addressing the issue have been informed by the contentions of parties and counsel, which, in turn, reflect the more general, societal discussion of same-sex marriage and its meaning that has occurred over the past decades⁶⁰.

He further concludes that “individuals need not await legislative action before asserting a fundamental right”⁶¹. That notion, even though unpopular, appears to be blooming. For example, two judges of the Constitutional Tribunal – Prof. Stelina and Dr. Zielonacki – both dissented from a decision to dismiss one of the constitutional complaints against Article 1 § 1 of The Family and Guardianship Code (which were discussed in Part A). The judges argued that the Tribunal should hear the case⁶². In his dissent Judge Zielonacki directly cited the *Obergefell* case, writing that “it’s impossible not to see a certain analogy—just as in the United States the right to same-sex marriage was derived from the constitutional guarantee of equal protection of private life and personal liberty, the complainants in this case attempt to replicate the same—knowingly referring to a nearly identical constitutional norm”, the norm being Article 31 § 1–2 of the Constitution⁶³.

But even though two Judges of the Polish Constitutional Tribunal seem to echo Kennedy’s sentiment – the truth remains that the level of discretion awarded to common law judges, precisely the power to strike down acts of legislature and statutes violating the Constitution⁶⁴, is incomparable to the power of their continental counterparts.

Unlike the Continental tradition, where the law is exclusively the product of the legislator, and judges are confined to applying the legislator’s law, in the American common

⁵⁸ Judgment of the CT of 24.10.2001, ref. SK 22/01.

⁵⁹ Order of the CT of 1.7.2021, ref. SK 15/17.

⁶⁰ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2015, *Obergefell v. Hodges*, 576 U.S. 644 (2015), p. 23.

⁶¹ Order of the CT of 1.7.2021, ref. SK 15/17.

⁶² Order of the CT of 1.7.2021, ref. SK 15/17 (J. Stelina, dissenting).

⁶³ Order of the CT of 1.7.2021, ref. SK 15/17 (A. Zielonacki, dissenting).

⁶⁴ See Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 24.2.1803, *Marbury v. Madison*, 5 U.S. (1 Cranch) 137 (1803).

law tradition the judge is an independent source of law and a check against the legislator's (unconstitutional) laws. (...) [J]udges within the American rule-of-law system at times follow the legislator, at times make law, and at other times strike down the legislator's law or the executive's decrees, thus using the powers of the state against the state itself. (...) The Continental judge, in contrast, operates in a single hierarchical system of law and is either subordinate to the legislator (the ordinary judge) or operates at the top of the constitutional pyramid as a superlegislator with confined powers delimited by the constitution (the constitutional judge). But whether ordinary judge or constitutional, the continental judge is always on the side of the state⁶⁵.

Article 178 § 1 of the national Constitution states that a judge is subject to the land's highest law as well as statutes established by the parliament, confirming the deep rootedness of Polish jurisprudence in the continental tradition⁶⁶. From that provision stems a rather logical conclusion, that judicial review of a sub-statutory act is generally permissible, as the judges are not strictly bound by such acts. Review of legal acts in scope of international law will be further explored in part 4 of the paper. And while the question whether an ordinary court may refuse to apply a statute facially incompatible with the Constitution is widely discussed and extremely controversial⁶⁷, there is no doubt that judges are not lawmakers and as such cannot issue *contra legem* interpretations in an attempt to circumvent the legislator's will – no matter how unequal or even unconstitutional that will may be. Such an assessment realistically precludes an *Obergefell*-like ruling from ever being handed down in Poland. That's because under national law, there's no court that would be entitled to issue such a decision. Of course, the Constitutional Tribunal could decide that provisions of The Family and Guardianship Code – in part that they do not guarantee an institutionalized form of same-sex marriage – are unconstitutional, but such an institutionalization would still need to be implemented by the legislature, not the judicature.

4. How Poland's international position makes *Windsor* relevant

However, we still ought to consider the decision in *United States v. Windsor*. What makes that ruling interesting is its ingenious use of the duality of the American legal system – that is the disjuncture between state and federal law. While writing the majority opinion Justice Kennedy did not even attempt to suggest that any provision of state law should be invalidated (although Justice Scalia, ultimately correctly, prophesized

⁶⁵ M. Rosenfeld, *Constitutional Adjudication in Europe and the United States: Paradoxes and Contrasts*, „International Journal of Constitutional Law” 2004, vol. 2, issue 4, October, p. 645–646.

⁶⁶ The Constitution of The Republic of Poland of 2.4.1997 (Journal of Laws No. 78, item 483, as amended), Article 178 § 1.

⁶⁷ See P. Wiliński, P. Karlik [in:] *Konstytucja RP. Tom II. Komentarz do art. 87–243*, ed. M. Safjan, L. Bosek, Warszawa 2016, commentary on Article 178, paras. 59–64 (summarizing conflicting interpretations regarding judicial subordination to the Constitution and statutes as specified in Article 178 § 1). See also: B. Naleziński [in:] *Konstytucja...*, commentary on Article 178.

such invalidations in his dissent)⁶⁸. Instead, the Court ordered just the federal government to recognize homosexual marriages, which essentially forced the states to do the same – that is, if they wanted to avoid chaos and legal uncertainty. Having that perspective in mind, we ought to acknowledge that a similar dualistic legal system operates in Poland. Indeed, national law is not the only source of legal norms that are applicable to its citizens, as the country is bound by various international agreements and is a member of numerous international organizations. For our considerations, the most crucial of those are the European Union and the Council of Europe.

Article 9 of the Constitution of Poland expresses the basic rule that *pacta servanda sunt*⁶⁹. Further provisions, contained in Chapter III, expand on that notion. Under Article 91 § 2–3 of the Constitution, international agreements ratified upon prior consent granted by statute as well as laws enacted by an organization established by such an agreement are directly applicable and have precedence over statutes in the event of a conflict of laws⁷⁰. Among countless acts ratified in this procedure was The European Convention on Human Rights⁷¹. Furthermore, Article 90 of the Constitution states that “the Republic of Poland may (...) delegate to an international organization or international institution the competence of organs of State authority in relation to certain matters” (such a delegation requires either a 2/3 supermajority of both houses of parliament, or the majority in a referendum)⁷². This provision has, as of January 2024, been exclusively used to ratify the EU Accession Treaty of 2003 (in a referendum)⁷³ and the Treaty of Lisbon of 2007 (by a supermajority)⁷⁴.

To consider whether the *Windsor* framework is workable under EU and CoE law we ought to look to one more group of regulations – that is, Polish national law on vital records (i.e., certificates of birth, marriage, and death). Article 104 § 5 of the Vital Records Act of 2014 makes it mandatory for Civil Registry Offices (USCs) to transcribe foreign vital records, should a Polish citizen request them to do so⁷⁵. § 2 of the same provision defines the act of transcription as a “literal and faithful transfer of data” from

⁶⁸ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 26.6.2013, *United States v. Windsor*, 570 U.S. 744 (2013), (Scalia, J., dissenting), p. 22–36.

⁶⁹ The Constitution of The Republic of Poland of 2.4.1997 (Journal of Laws No. 78, item 483, as amended), Article 9.

⁷⁰ The Constitution of The Republic of Poland of 2.4.1997 (Journal of Laws No. 78, item 483, as amended), Article 91 § 2–3.

⁷¹ Act of 2.10.1992 on the Ratification of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (Journal of Laws No. 85, item 427).

⁷² The Constitution of The Republic of Poland of 2.4.1997 (Journal of Laws No. 78, item 483, as amended), Article 90 § 1–4.

⁷³ Resolution of the Sejm of the Republic of Poland of 17.4.2003 on the calling of a nationwide referendum regarding consent for the ratification of the Treaty concerning the accession of the Republic of Poland to the European Union (Journal of Laws No. 66, item 613).

⁷⁴ Act of 1.4.2008 on the Ratification of the Treaty of Lisbon, amending the Treaty on the European Union and the Treaty Establishing the European Community, signed in Lisbon on 13.12.2007 (Journal of Laws No. 62, item 388).

⁷⁵ Act of 28.11.2014 – The Law on the Vital Records (consol. Journal of Laws of 2023 item 1378), Article 104 § 5.

the foreign record into the Polish registry⁷⁶. However, under Article 107 pt. 3 of the Act, the registry office may refuse to transcribe a vital record “if it would be inconsistent with the fundamental rules of the legal order of the Republic of Poland”⁷⁷. Another regulation, which has often become the base of transcription refusals, is Article 7 of the Private International Law Act of 2011, stating that “foreign law shall not be applied if its application would have effects incompatible with fundamental principles of the legal order of (...) Poland”⁷⁸. And while the SAC is persistent in ruling that transcribing same-sex marriage certificates would indeed be in violation of such fundamental rules and principles⁷⁹, the matter of records of birth is still heavily debated. That’s because transcribing such records is – in practice – necessary to issue a PESEL identification number and an ID card to a child born abroad, which makes it exceptionally difficult (if not outright impossible) for such a child to receive public education and to access the public health system in Poland⁸⁰. And yet, most if not all Heads of USCs are insistent on refusing to insert the names of same-sex parents into the registry under “Mother” and “Father”, as the law doesn’t provide for a gender-neutral noun, such as “Parent”. There are instances in which the SAC has reversed such refusals⁸¹ but its Resolution of December 2, 2019 – adopted by a panel of 7 judges, which binds all administrative courts in Poland⁸² – has explicitly affirmed such practices, explaining that in the Polish legal order a father must always be a male and a mother must always be a female⁸³. Such a stance has been mostly criticized in doctrine, although voices of approval are also present⁸⁴.

⁷⁶ Act of 28.11.2014 – The Law on the Vital Records (consol. Journal of Laws of 2023 item 1378), Article 104 § 2.

⁷⁷ Act of 28.11.2014 – The Law on the Vital Records (consol. Journal of Laws of 2023 item 1378), Article 107 point 3.

⁷⁸ The Act of 4.2.2011 – The International Private Law (consol. Journal of Laws of 2023 item 503), Article 7.

⁷⁹ See, e.g., Judgment of the SAC of 25.2.2020, ref. II OSK 1059/18; Judgment of the SAC of 22.6.2021, ref. II OSK 2608/19.

⁸⁰ *Dziecko tęczowej pary z zaświadczeniem zamiast aktu urodzenia. RPO ma uwagi*, para. 2, <<https://www.rp.pl/w-sadzie-i-w-urzedzie/art36743621-dziecko-teczowej-pary-z-zaswiadczeniem-zamiast-aktu-urodzenia-rpo-ma-uwagi>>, [accessed: 24.3.2023].

⁸¹ Judgment of the SAC of 10.10.2018, ref. II OSK 2552/16.

⁸² Act of 30.8.2002 – The Law on the Proceedings before the Administrative Courts (consol. Journal of Laws of 2023 item 163, as amended), Article 269 § 1.

⁸³ Resolution of the SAC of 2.12.2019, ref. II OPS 1/19.

⁸⁴ See M. Zachariasiewicz [in:] *Prawo prywatne międzynarodowe. Komentarz*, ed. M. Pazdan, Warszawa 2018, commentary on Article 7, paras. 44–48 (please note that Prof. Zachariasiewicz’s commentary was published before the SAC Resolution of 2.12.2019); T.J. Tadla, *Transkrypcja aktu stanu cywilnego. Glosa do uchwały NSA z dnia 2 grudnia 2019 r., II OPS 1/19*, „Państwo i Prawo” 2022, no. 3, p. 170–178; K. Drewniowska, *Glosa do uchwały NSA z dnia 2 grudnia 2019 r., II OPS 1/19*, „Przegląd Prawa i Administracji” 2021, no. 127, p. 547–562; A. Pudło-Jaremek, *Glosa do uchwały Naczelnego Sądu Administracyjnego z dnia 2 grudnia 2019 r., sygnatura akt II OPS 1/19*, „Roczniki Administracji i Prawa” 2020, no. 4, p. 281–288. Comp. M. Wojewoda, *Zagraniczne rodzicielstwo osób jednej płci a rejestracja stanu cywilnego w Polsce. Glosa do uchwały NSA z dnia 2 grudnia 2019 r., II OPS 1/19*, „Europejski Przegląd Sądowy” 2020, no. 8, p. 30–38.

It is worth noting that this interpretation has led to some truly bizarre situations, such as in the case of S.R.S.-D., who was born in Spain to a Polish mother and an Irish mother. The women were designated “Mother A” and “Mother B” on the Spain-issued birth certificate. Due to that fact, a Polish USC refused to transcribe the girl’s birth certificate. At the same time a passport office declined to issue an identity document for the child, as her birth record had not yet been transcribed. The mothers found themselves in a truly Kafkaesque situation, as the issuance of a passport relied on the transcription of the record, and vice versa. Even worse, Ireland had also refused to issue an ID card to the girl, as she was not eligible for Irish citizenship (since the Irish woman wasn’t her biological mother). The two mothers turned to the Polish Commissioner for Human Rights, who filed suit in a Kraków-based administrative court (the *RPO* case). The court sought a preliminary ruling from the European Court of Justice, which in turn decided that Poland must issue an identity document to the girl and recognize the Spanish birth certificate⁸⁵. The country is also obliged to respect the child’s right to move and reside freely within the Union with each of her two mothers, which is guaranteed by Article 21 § 1 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union⁸⁶ as interpreted by the Court’s landmark ruling in *Coman*⁸⁷. The Polish parliament has, as of January 2024, not yet implemented the ECJ’s ruling handed down in the *RPO* case. It must, however, be noted that the legislature is not the only body bound by the ECJ’s rulings. As the Court made clear nearly half a century ago in *Simmenthal*: “a national court which is called upon, within the limits of its jurisdiction, to apply provisions of Community law is under a duty to give full effect to those provisions, if necessary refusing of its own motion to apply any conflicting provision of national legislation, even if adopted subsequently, and it is not necessary for the court to request or await the prior setting aside of such provisions by legislative or other constitutional means”⁸⁸.

That validity of an EU law measure within a member state – as noted by the ECJ in *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft* – cannot be affected by allegations that it runs counter to either fundamental rights as formulated by the constitution of that state or the principles of its constitutional structure⁸⁹. Those arguments serve as the main basis for the doctrine of primacy of EU law as well as the correlated doctrine of direct effect. Those concepts are generally accepted, although most member states reserve the right to review whether EU legal acts lie within the competences delegated

⁸⁵ Order of the ECJ of 24.6.2023, *Rzecznik Praw Obywatelskich v K.S. and Others*, case C-2/21.

⁸⁶ Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (2012), Official Journal C 326, 26/10/2012, Article 21 § 1.

⁸⁷ Judgment of the ECJ (Grand Chamber) of 5.6.2018, *Coman and Others v Inspectoratul General pentru Imigrări and Ministerul Afacerilor Interne*, case C-673/16 (ECJ).

⁸⁸ Judgment of the ECJ of 9.3.1978, *Amministrazione delle finanze dello Stato v Simmenthal*, case C-106/77.

⁸⁹ Judgment of the ECJ of 17.12.1970, *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft mbH v Einfuhr- und Vorratsstelle für Getreide und Futtermittel*, case C-11/70.

to the Union under the Treaties⁹⁰. A body particularly active in this regard is the Polish Constitutional Tribunal, which has attempted to strike down many provisions of EU law⁹¹.

When analysing Poland's international obligations, it's impossible to disregard the rulings of another transnational court – that is the European Court of Human Rights. The ECtHR has for many years maintained that member states of the Council of Europe have a positive obligation to recognize same-sex couples⁹². The court has later elucidated, that while the states retain the autonomy to define the exact framework of same-sex unions in their national law, they must at the very least provide some form of recognition that protects the couples' interests⁹³. It must be noted that Poland was not a defendant in the Court's landmark gay-rights cases (*Oliari* and *Fedotova*) and as such was not explicitly bound by the decisions laid down in those proceedings. Only in December 2023, did the ECtHR issue its ruling in *Przybyszewska and Others v. Poland*, finding that the refusal to institutionalize same-sex unions violated Article 8 of the Convention (the right to privacy)⁹⁴. The Court concluded that “in the absence of official recognition (...) same-sex partners are unable to regulate fundamental aspects of their life, such as those concerning property, maintenance, taxation, and inheritance, as an officially recognised couple”⁹⁵. That decision, as of January 2024, can still be referred (appealed) to the Grand Chamber. However, should it become final, Poland will be – according to Article 46 of the Convention – bound to abide by the judgment⁹⁶. Precisely, the country would be obliged to take general measures, aiming to prevent similar violations from occurring⁹⁷. This obligation rests on the state, understood as the entirety of the public authorities⁹⁸. The Polish Supreme Court has explicitly ruled that such an understanding of the state also extends to the judiciary: “The duty to respect the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights is therefore also incumbent on the courts. This involves not only considering the Court's position when interpreting the provisions of the Convention and interpreting

⁹⁰ D. Kornobis-Romanowska, *Rozdział X. Relacje pomiędzy prawem Unii Europejskiej a prawem krajowym państw członkowskich* [in:] *Prawo Unii Europejskiej*, ed. J. Barcik, R. Grzeszczak, Warszawa 2022, p. 318–319.

⁹¹ D. Kornobis-Romanowska, *Rozdział X...*, p. 321–322. See also: Judgment of the CT of 7.10.2021, K 3/21.

⁹² Judgment of the ECtHR of 21.7.2015, *Oliari and Others v. Italy*, application nos. 18766/11 and 36030/11.

⁹³ Judgment of the ECtHR of 13.7.2021, *Fedotova and Others v. Russia*, applications nos. 40792/10 and 2 others.

⁹⁴ Judgment of the ECtHR of 12.12.2023, *Przybyszewska and Others v. Poland*, applications nos. 11454/17 and 9 others.

⁹⁵ Judgment of the ECtHR of 12.12.2023, *Przybyszewska and Others v. Poland*, applications nos. 11454/17 and 9 others.

⁹⁶ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (1950), Council of Europe Treaty Series 005, Article 46.

⁹⁷ *Guide on Article 46 of the European Convention on Human Rights*, ECtHR 2022, p. 8, <https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/d/echr/Guide_Art_46_ENG>, [accessed: 28.1.2024].

⁹⁸ R. Degener, L. Garlicki, P. Hofmański, A. Wróbel [in:] *Konwencja o Ochronie Praw Człowieka i Podstawowych Wolności. Komentarz do artykułów 19–59 oraz Protokołów dodatkowych*, vol. II, ed. L. Garlicki, Warszawa 2011, commentary on Article 46, para. 39.

national laws in accordance with this interpretation, but also taking **concrete measures** to comply with the Court's judgment [emphasis – M.C.]⁹⁹.

5. Conclusion

It's impossible to overlook the similarities between the concerns Poland is facing today, and the ones the U.S. battled nearly a decade ago. Importantly, in America, the outright issue that the courts had to weigh in on wasn't whether gay people were allowed to marry. First, they needed to establish whether same-sex marriages officiated in other jurisdictions (such as Canada) should be recognized by the federal government and whether the spouses could receive certain benefits, which they would be entitled to if it weren't for their sex. That question was conclusively answered in the *Windsor* ruling, where the Supreme Court decided that excluding homosexual people from federal tax exemptions or the next-of-kin status constituted illegal discrimination. The federal and state governments were thus forced to essentially recognize same-sex marriages which were considered valid in other jurisdictions. After the ruling, the support for marriage equality in the U.S. rose from 45% to 53% in 2012¹⁰⁰ and 60% in 2015¹⁰¹. The ruling in *Obergefell* soon followed and, amid the newformed consensus, finally implemented full marriage equality.

Nowadays, in the EU same-sex people are legally allowed to marry in 15 countries while 7 others allow them to enter into civil unions¹⁰². Poland – along with 4 other states – finds itself in a difficult spot. That's because international law is very clear – under the ECJ's ruling in *RPO* the country is obliged to allow same-sex couples to move and reside freely¹⁰³. Those couples also have a reasonable expectation to access certain benefits, such as public education for their children or marital tax exemptions. Meanwhile, under the ECtHR's ruling in *Przybyszewska* Poland ought to outright recognize and afford the necessary protections to same-sex unions¹⁰⁴. Those duties (as discussed in part 4) fall not only on the legislature but also on the judiciary, simultaneously preceding duties arising out of national law regulations, even those of constitutional rank (for example – the regulation of Article 18 of the Constitution). It should be noted that the courts are fully aware of that obligation. One proof of such awareness is a decision of the SAC issued in November 2023, in which the Court decided to seek a preliminary ruling from the ECJ on whether EU law requires a member state to recognize and transcribe same-sex marriage certificates issued in another country¹⁰⁵. Should

⁹⁹ Judgment of the SC of 28.11.2008, ref. V CSK 271/08.

¹⁰⁰ Judgment of the Supreme Court of Poland of 28.11.2008, ref. V CSK 271/08.

¹⁰¹ J. McCarthy, *Record-High 60% of Americans Support Same-Sex Marriage*, <<https://news.gallup.com/poll/183272/record-high-americans-support-sex-marriage.aspx>>, [accessed: 2.4.2023].

¹⁰² *Marriage...*

¹⁰³ Order of the ECJ of 24.6.2023, *Rzecznik Praw Obywatelskich v K.S. and Others*, case C-2/21.

¹⁰⁴ Judgment of the ECtHR of 12.12.2023, *Przybyszewska and Others v. Poland*, applications nos. 11454/17 and 9 others.

¹⁰⁵ Order of the SAC of 8.11.2023, ref. II OSK 216/21.

the ECJ answer in the affirmative – finding that a gay marriage officiated in e.g. Spain should be considered valid in Poland – the gravity of such a ruling would be directly comparable to that of *Windsor*. After all, should Poland be forced recognize some same-sex marriages, it would be difficult to argue why it should exclude others.

The U.S. Supreme Court’s decisions in *United States v. Windsor* and *Obergefell v. Hodges* express the belief that marriage is a fundamental human right. Both opinions, authored by Justice Kennedy, echo another landmark ruling, that is *Loving v. Virginia* – the case that legalized interracial marriage¹⁰⁶. It was in this 1967 decision that Chief Justice Warren wrote: “marriage is one of the ‘basic civil rights of man,’ fundamental to our very existence and survival. (...) To deny this fundamental freedom on so un-supportable a basis as the racial classifications (...), classifications so directly subversive of the principle of equality at the heart of the Fourteenth Amendment, is surely to deprive all the State’s citizens of liberty without due process of law”¹⁰⁷.

The *Loving* ruling sparked major controversy back in 1967 – especially in the south. Yet today it seems almost unthinkable to deny someone the right to marry on account of skin color. After all, the government has no rational interest in denying two consenting adults an institutionalized form of recognition while bestowing such a right upon others. Almost half a decade later the same exact logic was applied to same-sex couples. It is plausible to think that in another 50 years our descendants will consider discrimination due to sexual orientation equally preposterous as the mid-20th century racism.

As the Ipsos poll (cited in part 2) shows, the level of social acceptance concerning same-sex marriage in Poland is steadily rising. And it’s true that “the defense of marriage” or “protecting children from the LGBT ideology” – terms which the incumbent Polish president used in his reelection campaign – are convenient slogans¹⁰⁸. And yet, those phrases are nothing new. In 1967, in the *Loving* case Robert D. McIlwaine III argued that “from the psycho-sociological point of view, interracial marriages are detrimental to the individual, to the family, and to society” and that they are “wrong because they are most frequently (...) entered into (...) by people who have a rebellious attitude (...) towards society”¹⁰⁹. The religious arguments were also plentiful¹¹⁰. Additionally, a Gallup Poll shows that in June 1968 – just one year after *Loving* – 73% of Americans still disapproved of marriage between White and Black people. Today, such a stance is considered unthinkable.

The situation in Poland is currently a direct reflection of the United States at a pre-*Windsor* stage. Even though the inequality is unquestionable, a legislative solution is unlikely. The land’s highest courts are also unwilling to rule on the matter,

¹⁰⁶ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 12.6.1967, *Loving v. Virginia*, 388 U.S. 1 (1967).

¹⁰⁷ Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 12.6.1967, *Loving v. Virginia*, 388 U.S. 1 (1967), p. 12.

¹⁰⁸ J. Hartman, *Duda wszczyzna wojnę ideową. Karta Rodziny punkt po punkcie*, <<https://www.polityka.pl/tygodnikpolityka/kraj/1959952,1,duda-wszczyzna-wojne-ideowa-karta-rodziny-punkt-po-punkcie.read>>, [accessed: 9.4.2023].

¹⁰⁹ *Loving v. Virginia Oral Argument*, April 1967, <<https://www.oyez.org/cases/1966/395>>, [accessed: 9.4.2023].

¹¹⁰ See, e.g., Decision of the U.S. Supreme Court of 12.6.1967, *Loving v. Virginia*, 388 U.S. 1 (1967), p. 1.

instead futilely awaiting a decision of the Sejm. Meanwhile, the pressure to recognize same-sex unions both at home and abroad is increasing. As this paper established, the legal basis for recognizing same-sex marriages already exists. And even though Polish ordinary courts are unable to strike down acts of the legislature or outright create a legislative solution of their own (as discussed in part 3), they do possess some lawmaking capacities. In *United States v. Windsor*, the U.S. Supreme Court decided that a tax privilege awarded to heterosexual marriages should be extended to homosexual couples. The arguments brought up in that decision do indeed hold up in the Polish legal system. The national courts are thus able – or even obliged, under international law – to confer some privileges upon homosexual couples. The administrative courts may, for example, order the transcriptions of vital records or maybe even extend some tax benefits to same-sex couples, as they scrutinize the decisions of the USCAs and Tax Offices. And even though a ruling such as *Obergefell* should be considered impermissible under Polish law, as the U.S. cases show, the road from the pre-*Windsor* hostility to a well-established national consensus seems to be short.

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